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The Decision-Making Skills of Public Elementary School Principals: Inputs for a Proposed Action Plan

Moonrose DS. Pesano, * Melchor Espiritu
For affiliations and correspondence, see the last page.

Abstract

This study aimed to determine the decision-making skills of school administrators, which served as input for a proposed action plan during the school year 2024-2025. Regarding analytical skills, the school administrator respondents got a composite mean of 3.45, while the teacher respondents got 3.47, both of which were verbally interpreted as very likely. Regarding Behavioral Skills, the school administrator-respondents got a composite mean of 3.35, while the teacher-respondents got 3.51 verbally interpreted as Very likely. Regarding conceptual skill, the school administrator respondents got a composite mean of 3.48, while the teacher respondents got 3.41, both verbally interpreted as very likely. Regarding Directive Skill, the school administrator-respondents got a composite mean of 3.62, while the teacher-respondents got 3.46, both verbally interpreted as Very likely. There is no significant difference between the perceptions of the two groups of respondents regarding the decision-making skills of school administrators concerning the above-mentioned variables.

Keywords: *decision making, school administrators, teacher*

Introduction

School administrators constitute the administrative staff who have to make decisions concerning the running of schools. They do the planning, organizing, leading, and monitoring required for schools to function and deal with various situations. While undertaking these tasks and managerial responsibilities, and when dealing with situations, school principals must make decisions by considering internal and external factors. At this point, the determining factor is the system within which school administrators have to make decisions.

An effective decision-making process deals with coordinating both human and material resources. This is built on the principle that effective school administration involves periodically assessing teachers' tasks and students' performance. This is done to check deviations and distortions to the stated objectives. It is, therefore, an important task of the school principal to assess how, when, and the extent to which decisions and functions are performed by teachers. At the same time, the feedback received is also used to ensure effective control to achieve the stated objectives.

According to Simon (2019), school administrators need to master the concept of administrative decision-making. Theories of how administrators make decisions changed dramatically when the administrative decision-making model began replacing the classic rational model of decision-making. Simon's studies of administrators' decision-making processes indicated that most administrators made decisions inconsistent with the classic rational model. The rational approach involves gathering and using data to decide how to solve a problem. The model assumes that the person making the decision has all the information needed to consider possible alternatives and that the alternatives will address the problem.

In addition, Klein (2019) postulated organizational and decision-making concepts. He stated that the culture and structure of the organization affect how decisions are made. Some organizations espouse the philosophy that problems are challenges and that members of organizations can learn to recognize novel problems. However, the decision-making processes, constraints, and the personal characteristics of the individuals involved also affect decision-making.

Certainly, school administrators are among the main actors responsible for decision-making in the daily running of schools. However, how they tend to act in terms of decision-making during organizational change requires further investigation.

It is on considering the above perspectives that this study was conceptualized. Specifically, it intends to determine the decision-making skills of the school administrators to determine the impact or effect of the decision-making process implemented by the school administrators on school performance and to propose an action plan that would strengthen the decision-making skills of the school administrators.

Research Questions

This study aimed to determine the decision-making skills of school administrators which served as inputs for a proposed action plan during the school year 2024-2025. More specifically, it sought answers to the following questions:

1. What is the perception of the school administrators themselves and the teachers as regards the decision-making skills of school administrators in terms of the following:
 - 1.1. analytical skill;
 - 1.2. behavioral skill;
 - 1.3. conceptual skill; and

- 1.4. directive skill?
2. Is there a significant difference between the perceptions of the two groups of respondents as regards the decision-making skills of school administrators with respect to the above-mentioned variables?
3. Based on the results of the study, what action plan of decision-making skills may be proposed?

Methodology

Research Design

The study employed a descriptive survey research design. The study will give a detailed description of the school administrators' management of teachers' professional development and its effect on teachers' classroom practices and pupils' academic performance. According to Gay (2019), descriptive research involves collecting data to test hypotheses or to answer questions concerning the current status of the subject of the study. A descriptive study determines and reports the way things are. Descriptive research systematically deals with certain areas or populations about events, phenomena, or facts.

A descriptive study determines and reports the way things are. Descriptive research systematically deals with certain areas or populations about events, phenomena, or facts.

The descriptive research method primarily focuses on describing the nature of a demographic segment without focusing on "why" a particular phenomenon occurs. In other words, it "describes" the research subject without covering "why" it happens.

Respondents

The researcher used purposive sampling. This was conducted in the selected schools of District 2D, Division of Antipolo City. The study respondents were school administrators and teachers. Each instrument was administered to all the respondents. The respondents were given enough time to answer the research instrument. The scope of this study covered the School Administrators and teachers from the selected schools of District 2D, Division of Antipolo City.

Instrument

The study used a researcher-made questionnaire and descriptive questions that served as indicators in every variable. The survey questionnaire consisted of three parts. The first part contained the evaluation of the respondents. The second part contained the school performance rating, and the third part contained the comments and suggestions of the school administrator and teacher respondents.

The questionnaires that served as survey instruments of the study were validated by experts to ensure their correctness and validity. The questionnaire's contents were analyzed and scrutinized by principals, master teachers, English teachers, and education program supervisors. Their comments and feedback were considered in the final approval of the method and were examined by the consultant again as the researcher's proofreader.

Procedure

Permission from the concerned authorities was sought before the conduct of the study. Upon approval of the school's division superintendent and the principal, the questionnaire – checklists were administered to the school administrator and teacher-respondents from the selected public elementary schools of District 2D, Division of Antipolo City, and were personally retrieved by the researcher.

Data Analysis

Frequency, Percentage Distribution, and Ranking. This was used to analyze and summarize the results of the responses from the questionnaire.

t-Test. This was used to determine the significant difference between the perceptions of the two groups of respondents as regards the decision-making skills of school administrators.

Results and Discussion

This section provided the presentation, analysis, and interpretation of the gathered data from the questionnaires answered by the respondents in accordance with the specific questions posited on the objectives of the study.

Based on School Administrator's Perception

Perception of the school administrators as regards the decision-making skills in terms of Analytical Skill

As discussed in Table 1, the respondents stated that they trust my intuition in producing solutions to the current problem, which got the highest weighted mean of 3.63 and the highest rank of 1. The findings indicated that teachers trusted the school principal's intuition in producing solutions to current problems within the school community. Principals were perceived as insightful and capable leaders who could effectively address and resolve challenges. Teachers recognized the principal's ability to assess situations accurately and make informed decisions based on a deep understanding of the school's dynamics. Principals demonstrated a keen sense of judgment and proactive problem-solving skills, which instilled confidence among staff members. Behaviour analytic interventions may effectively

support skill development in young children with intellectual disabilities, meeting criteria for established interventions in communication, adaptive, and pre-academic skills (Ho et al., 2020).

Table 1. *Perception of the school administrators as regards the decision-making skills in terms of Analytical Skill*

<i>As a principal, I...</i>	<i>A. Analytical Skill</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>	<i>Rank</i>
1. try to obtain every detail and all technical information related to the problem.		3.37	Very Likely	3
2. make decisions based on the data available.		3.34	Very Likely	4
3. try to find innovative solutions to problems.		3.33	Very Likely	5
4. prefer to think about the problem superficially.		3.57	Very Likely	2
5. trust my intuition in producing solutions to the current problem.		3.63	Very Likely	1
Composite Mean		3.45	Very Likely	

However, the said group of respondents stated that they try to find innovative solutions to problems which yielded the least weighted mean of 3.33 and least rank of 5. The findings indicated that school principals consistently sought innovative solutions to problems within the school community. Principals were perceived as forward-thinking leaders who actively explored new ideas and approaches to address challenges and enhance the overall educational experience. Principals demonstrated a commitment to creativity and innovation by encouraging a culture of experimentation and open-mindedness among teachers and staff. They promoted the use of new technologies, teaching methods, and instructional strategies to improve student engagement and learning outcomes. Toleva-Stoimenova and Rasheva-Yordanova (2023) stated that analytical thinking is crucial for university education, and tools like research-based education, problem-based education, and game-based education can help improve it.

The composite mean of 3.45 implied that the perception of the school administrators as regards the decision-making skills in terms of Analytical Skill is in high level. The findings indicated that school administrators were perceived to have a high level of decision-making skills, particularly in terms of analytical skills. Administrators demonstrated strong abilities in analyzing complex situations, evaluating data, and making informed decisions that positively impacted the school community. Administrators were recognized for their systematic approach to problem-solving, carefully examining all relevant factors and considering multiple perspectives before reaching conclusions. They effectively utilized data and evidence to guide their decisions, ensuring that their actions were grounded in factual information and aligned with the school's goals and priorities. According to Suyatman et al. (2021), implementing the Problem-Based Learning (PBL) model significantly improves students' analytical thinking skills in the concept of new and renewable energy compared to a control group.

Perception of the school administrators as regards the decision-making skills in terms of Behavioral Skill

Table 2. *Perception of the school administrators as regards the decision-making skills in terms of Behavioral Skill*

<i>As a principal, I...</i>	<i>B. Behavioral Skill</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>	<i>Rank</i>
1. believe that social relations in my school are at the heart of decision-making processes.		3.35	Very Likely	3
2. refrain from making long-term analyses when making a decision.		3.52	Very Likely	1
3. think about how it will affect those on the receiving end in any decision-making process.		3.22	Likely	5
4. try to carefully review/consider everything related to the problem in any decision-making process.		3.29	Very Likely	4
5. disregard social relations in my school when making a decision, if necessary.		3.37	Very Likely	2
Composite Mean		3.35	Very Likely	

As presented in Table 2, the respondents perceived that they refrain from making long-term analyses when making a decision which got the highest weighted mean of 3.52 and the highest rank of 1. The findings indicated that school administrators refrained from making long-term analyses when making decisions. This approach suggested a preference for addressing immediate needs and concerns over considering potential future implications and long-term strategies. Administrators focused on resolving pressing issues and implementing solutions that provided quick and effective results. This decision-making style was likely driven by the need to respond promptly to the dynamic and often urgent challenges within the school environment. School administrators' behaviors, such as administrative, effective communication, personality traits, and meeting social needs, positively impact teachers' professional belonging (Özdoğru, 2022).

However, the said group of respondents observed that they think about how it will affect those on the receiving end in any decision-making process which yielded the least weighted mean of 3.22 and least rank of 5. The findings indicated that school administrators consistently considered the impact of their decisions on those on the receiving end during the decision-making process. This approach demonstrated a high level of empathy and a commitment to ensuring that the needs and perspectives of all stakeholders were taken into account. Administrators prioritized understanding how their decisions would affect students, teachers, parents, and other members of the school community. They engaged in active listening and sought feedback from various stakeholders to gain a comprehensive understanding of their concerns, needs, and aspirations. According to Özdemir et al (2021), school principals' 21st century skills, particularly information literacy, technology literacy, accountability, leadership, and responsibility, significantly predict their strategic

leadership behaviors.

The composite mean of 3.35 implied that the perception of the school administrators as regards the decision-making skills in terms of behavioral skill is in high level. The findings indicated that school administrators were perceived to have a high level of decision-making skills, particularly in terms of behavioral skills. Administrators demonstrated strong interpersonal and emotional intelligence, which played a crucial role in their effective decision-making processes. Administrators were recognized for their ability to build positive relationships and foster a supportive environment within the school community. They effectively communicated their decisions and the rationale behind them, ensuring transparency and fostering trust among teachers, students, and parents. Çaybaş & Ordu (2022) stated that school administrators have high communication skills, particularly in giving confidence, but lower in giving feedback, with significant differences across branches, teacher tenure, school type, and teacher number.

Perception of the school administrators as regards the decision-making skills in terms of Conceptual Skill

Table 3. Perception of the school administrators as regards the decision-making skills in terms of Conceptual Skill

<i>C. Conceptual Skill</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>	<i>Rank</i>
<i>As a principal, I...</i>			
1. understand that decision-making is a process that involves risk-taking.	3.24	Likely	5
2. consider ethical and value-based issues carefully when making any decision.	3.43	Very Likely	3
3. believe in the necessity of sharing power and authority in the decision-making process.	3.30	Very Likely	4
4. try to be careful not to cause negative consequences in the decision-making process.	3.72	Very Likely	1
5. know that rationality/logic is the most important thing guiding me in decision-making.	3.70	Very Likely	2
Composite Mean	3.48	Very Likely	

As shown in Table 3, the respondents perceived that they try to be careful not to cause negative consequences in the decision-making process which got the highest weighted mean of 3.72 and the highest rank of 1. The findings indicated that school administrators made a concerted effort to avoid causing negative consequences in the decision-making process. They demonstrated a high level of conscientiousness and foresight, ensuring that their actions were thoughtful and well-considered to minimize any adverse impacts. Administrators carefully evaluated potential outcomes and implications of their decisions, taking a proactive approach to identify and mitigate risks. They sought input from various stakeholders to gain diverse perspectives and anticipate potential challenges, ensuring that their decisions were well-informed and balanced. Mentoring for school administrators' professional development has evolved from networking to leadership skills, with the most recent focus on enhancing mentoring quality and enabling social justice (Yirci et al., 2023).

However, the said group of respondents stated that they understand that decision-making is a process that involves risk-taking which yielded the least weighted mean of 3.24 and least rank of 5. The findings indicated that school administrators understood that decision-making is a process involving risk-taking. They recognized that making impactful decisions often required stepping into uncertain territories and balancing potential rewards against possible challenges. Administrators demonstrated a pragmatic approach to decision-making, acknowledging that not all outcomes could be predicted with certainty. They were prepared to take calculated risks when necessary to drive innovation, improve educational outcomes, and address pressing issues within the school community. According to Atiş & Dilbaz (2022), school administrators should develop human, technical, and organizational skills to increase school effectiveness, as identified by teachers.

The composite mean of 3.48 implied that the perception of the school administrators as regards the decision-making skills in terms of conceptual skill is in high level. The findings indicated that school administrators were perceived to have a high level of decision-making skills, particularly in terms of conceptual skills. Administrators demonstrated strong abilities in understanding and integrating complex ideas, which allowed them to develop comprehensive and strategic solutions to challenges within the school community. Administrators were recognized for their ability to see the big picture and connect various elements of the school environment. They effectively synthesized information from multiple sources, identifying key trends and underlying issues that required attention. This holistic approach enabled them to make decisions that were well-rounded and forward-thinking. Adhikari & Budhathoki (2023) stated that head teachers need technical, interpersonal, and conceptual administrative skills to effectively lead educational institutions and improve student academic achievement.

Perception of the school administrators as regards the decision-making skills in terms of Directive Skill

As presented in Table 4, the respondents stated that they try to produce as many different alternatives as possible when making a decision which got the highest weighted mean of 3.75 and the highest rank of 1. The findings indicated that school administrators made a concerted effort to produce as many different alternatives as possible when making a decision. They recognized the value of exploring a wide range of options to ensure that the most effective and innovative solutions were identified. Administrators demonstrated a commitment to thoroughness in their decision-making process by considering multiple perspectives and potential courses of action. They actively encouraged brainstorming sessions, collaborative discussions, and input from various stakeholders to generate diverse ideas and approaches. School principals highly enforce the skills in the School Leaders Empowerment Program, with administrative achievement being the highest, followed by technical achievement in student improvement, teaching skill improvement, and quality improvement (Al-Khamis & Al-Qahtani, 2023).

Table 4. Perception of the school administrators as regards the decision-making skills in terms of Directive Skill

<i>D. Directive Skill</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>	<i>Rank</i>
<i>As a principal, I...</i>			
1. feel time pressure in the decision-making process.	3.73	Very Likely	2
2. tend to make a choice from among the options in the decision-making process.	3.49	Very Likely	5
3. expect to see/feel everyone's respect for the decision I have made.	3.50	Very Likely	4
4. try to produce as many different alternatives as possible when making a decision.	3.75	Very Likely	1
5. consider the idea that every decision should be based on extensive/careful evaluations.	3.65	Very Likely	3
Composite Mean	3.62	Very Likely	

However, the said group of respondents stated that they tend to make a choice from among the options in the decision-making process which yielded the least weighted mean of 3.49 and least rank of 5. The findings indicated that school administrators tended to make choices from among the options generated during the decision-making process. While they actively sought diverse alternatives and perspectives, administrators ultimately focused on evaluating and selecting the most viable and effective option to address the school's needs and challenges. Administrators demonstrated a pragmatic approach to decision-making by carefully assessing each alternative against established criteria and priorities. They considered factors such as feasibility, impact on student outcomes, resource implications, and alignment with the school's mission and values. According to Karmila et al (2023), principal's administrative competency and teacher's professional competence both significantly impact educational quality in public senior high schools.

The composite mean of 3.62 implied that the perception of the school administrators as regards the decision-making skills in terms of directive skills is in high level. The findings indicated that school administrators were perceived to have a high level of decision-making skills, particularly in terms of directive skills. Administrators demonstrated strong leadership abilities and a decisive approach to decision-making, effectively guiding the school community through various challenges and opportunities. Administrators were recognized for their ability to provide clear direction and set strategic priorities for the school. They articulated a compelling vision and goals, ensuring alignment with the school's mission and values. This clarity in direction enabled administrators to effectively communicate expectations and rally stakeholders around common objectives. Luther (2020) stated that school administrators play a crucial role in recruiting, retaining, and respecting early childhood educators, ensuring that children receive the skills necessary for success in later grades.

Based on Teachers Perception

Perception of the teachers as regards the decision-making skills of school administrators in terms of Analytical Skill

Table 5. Perception of the teachers as regards the decision-making skills of school administrators in terms of Analytical Skill

<i>A. Analytical Skill</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>	<i>Rank</i>
<i>The principal...</i>			
1. try to obtain every detail and all technical information related to the problem.	3.63	Very Likely	1
2. make decisions based on the data available.	3.43	Very Likely	3
3. try to find innovative solutions to problems.	3.35	Very Likely	5
4. prefer to think about the problem superficially.	3.37	Very Likely	4
5. trust my intuition in producing solutions to the current problem.	3.57	Very Likely	2
Composite Mean	3.47	Very Likely	

As discussed in Table 5, the respondents stated that the school administrator try to obtain every detail and all technical information related to the problem, which got the highest weighted mean of 3.63 and the highest rank of 1. The findings indicated that school administrators made a concerted effort to obtain every detail and all technical information related to problems encountered within the school community. Administrators were recognized for their thoroughness and attention to detail in gathering comprehensive data and understanding the complexities of various issues. Administrators demonstrated a proactive approach to problem-solving by conducting thorough research, consulting experts, and analyzing relevant data and information. They sought to gain a deep understanding of the root causes and underlying factors contributing to challenges faced by the school. Critical and analytical thinking skills are significantly correlated in ecology learning, with analytical thinking skills having a positive effect on critical thinking skills (Mayarni & Nopiyanti, 2021).

However, the said group of respondents stated that the school administrators try to find innovative solutions to problems which yielded the least weighted mean of 3.35 and least rank of 5. The findings indicated that school administrators actively sought innovative solutions to address challenges within the school community. Administrators were recognized for their proactive approach to problem-solving, emphasizing creativity and out-of-the-box thinking to foster continuous improvement and adaptability. Administrators encouraged a culture of innovation by supporting and empowering teachers, staff, and stakeholders to explore new ideas and experiment with novel approaches. They promoted brainstorming sessions, collaborative discussions, and professional development opportunities focused on innovative practices and solutions. In relation Fadly (2021) stated that analytical thinking skills in students vary based on their learning styles, with visual style subjects explaining more, audiovisual subjects simplifying, and kinesthetic subjects applying unique concepts.

The composite mean of 3.47 implied that the school administrators as perceived by the teachers regards the decision-making skills in terms of Analytical Skill is in high level. The perception among teachers regarding school administrators' decision-making skills, particularly in terms of analytical skill, was consistently high. Teachers viewed administrators as adept at analyzing complex information and data to make informed decisions that positively impacted the school environment. Administrators demonstrated a strong ability to assess situations critically and objectively. They effectively utilized data and evidence to evaluate different options and predict potential outcomes, ensuring that decisions were based on thorough analysis rather than instinct or preference. According to Albalawi (2023), academic administrators with reflective thinking and problem-solving skills are more effective in managing educational institutions and promoting ethical behavior.

Perception of the teachers as regards the decision-making skills of the school administrators in terms of Behavioral Skill

Table 6. *Perception of the teachers as regards the decision-making skills of the school administrators in terms of Behavioral Skill*

<i>The principal...</i>	<i>B. Behavioral Skill</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>	<i>Rank</i>
1. believe that social relations in my school are at the heart of decision-making processes.		3.73	Very Likely	1
2. refrain from making long-term analyses when making a decision.		3.51	Very Likely	3
3. think about how it will affect those on the receiving end in any decision-making process.		3.67	Very Likely	2
4. try to carefully review/consider everything related to the problem in any decision-making process.		3.22	Likely	5
5. disregard social relations in my school when making a decision, if necessary.		3.42	Very Likely	4
	Composite Mean	3.51	Very Likely	

As presented in Table 6, the respondents perceived that the school administrators believe that social relations in my school are at the heart of decision-making processes which got the highest weighted mean of 3.73 and the highest rank of 1. The school administrators believe that social relations are at the heart of decision-making processes within the school community. They recognize the importance of fostering positive relationships and open communication among stakeholders as foundational to effective decision-making. Administrators prioritize building a supportive and collaborative school culture where trust, respect, and empathy guide interactions. They value the input and perspectives of teachers, students, parents, and staff, viewing these relationships as essential in understanding diverse needs and viewpoints. School administrators with neuroticism, extroversion, and agreeableness personality traits are significant predictors of their communication competences, while responsibility and openness to experience are not significant (Bozkurt et al., 2023).

However, the said group of respondents observed that the school administrators try to carefully review/consider everything related to the problem in any decision-making process which yielded the least weighted mean of 3.22 and least rank of 5. The school administrators strive to carefully review and consider every aspect related to problems in any decision-making process. They are dedicated to a thorough and meticulous approach, ensuring that decisions are well-informed and effectively address the challenges faced by the school community. Administrators demonstrate a commitment to gathering comprehensive information and data relevant to the problem at hand. They engage in detailed research, consult with stakeholders, and analyze various perspectives to gain a holistic understanding of the issue. According to Gómez-Leal et al. (2021), emotional intelligence, particularly self-awareness, self-management, and empathy, is crucial for effective school leadership, leading to improved teacher satisfaction and performance.

The composite mean of 3.51 implied that the school administrators as perceived by the teachers regards the decision-making skills in terms of behavioral skill is in high level. The perception among teachers regarding school administrators' decision-making skills, particularly in terms of behavioral skills, was consistently high. Teachers viewed administrators as effective leaders who demonstrated strong interpersonal abilities and emotional intelligence in their decision-making processes. Administrators were recognized for their ability to foster positive relationships and cultivate a supportive school culture. They demonstrated empathy, active listening, and sensitivity to the needs and concerns of teachers, students, and parents, which informed their decisions and actions. Mariyadas & Saravanakumar (2023) stated that high emotional intelligence in school principals is associated with a 75% relationship with effective confrontational resolving skills in conflict resolution.

Perception of the teachers as regards the decision-making skills of the school administrators in terms of Conceptual Skill

Table 7. *Perception of the teachers as regards the decision-making skills of the school administrators in terms of Conceptual Skill*

<i>The principal...</i>	<i>C. Conceptual Skill</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>	<i>Rank</i>
1. understand that decision-making is a process that involves risk-taking.		3.69	Very Likely	1
2. consider ethical and value-based issues carefully when making any decision.		3.39	Very Likely	2
3. believe in the necessity of sharing power and authority in the decision-making process.		3.32	Very Likely	4
4. try to be careful not to cause negative consequences in the decision-making process.		3.36	Very Likely	3
5. know that rationality/logic is the most important thing guiding me in decision-making.		3.30	Very Likely	5
	Composite Mean	3.41	Very Likely	

As shown in Table 7, the respondents perceived that the school administrators understand that decision-making is a process that involves risk-taking which got the highest weighted mean of 3.69 and the highest rank of 1. The school administrators understand that decision-making is a process that inherently involves risk-taking. They recognize that making impactful decisions often requires navigating uncertainty and weighing potential outcomes against potential risks. Administrators approach decision-making with a balanced perspective, acknowledging that taking calculated risks can lead to innovation, growth, and positive change within the school community. They encourage a culture that embraces thoughtful risk assessment and strategic planning to minimize potential negative impacts while maximizing opportunities for improvement. Hussain et al. (2023) stated that public secondary schools have better administrators' supervision and teachers' pedagogical skills, leading to better alignment with the Minimum Quality Standards for Schooling and the Sustainable Development Goals.

However, the said group of respondents stated that the school administrators know that rationality/logic is the most important thing guiding them in decision-making which yielded the least weighted mean of 3.30 and least rank of 5. The school administrators prioritize rationality and logic as fundamental guiding principles in their decision-making processes. They understand that making informed and effective decisions requires a systematic approach that is grounded in sound reasoning and critical analysis. Administrators emphasize the importance of gathering relevant data, information, and evidence to inform their decisions. They utilize analytical tools and frameworks to assess different options objectively and evaluate potential outcomes based on logical reasoning. Managerial skills, specifically financial and administrative skills, significantly influence the performance of School Management Committees in primary schools (Burani & Rashid, 2023).

The composite mean of 3.41 implied that the school administrators as perceived by the teachers regards the decision-making skills in terms of conceptual skill is in high level. The teachers perceive school administrators to possess high-level decision-making skills, particularly in terms of conceptual skill. Administrators are recognized for their ability to conceptualize and strategize effectively, demonstrating a deep understanding of educational principles, organizational dynamics, and the broader context in which decisions are made. Administrators excel in connecting complex ideas and information, synthesizing diverse perspectives, and envisioning long-term goals and outcomes for the school community. They leverage their conceptual skills to develop innovative solutions to challenges, aligning decisions with the school's mission and vision. Principals' managerial skills include technical, human, and conceptual abilities, which are crucial for successfully implementing School-Based Management in education (Shofwa, 2022).

Perception of the teachers as regards the decision-making skills of the school administrators in terms of Directive Skill

Table 8. Perception of the teachers as regards the decision-making skills of the school administrators in terms of Directive Skill

<i>D. Directive Skill</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>	<i>Rank</i>
<i>The principal...</i>			
1. feel time pressure in the decision-making process.	3.30	Very Likely	5
2. tend to make a choice from among the options in the decision-making process.	3.74	Very Likely	1
3. expect to see/feel everyone's respect for the decision I have made.	3.33	Very Likely	4
4. try to produce as many different alternatives as possible when making a decision.	3.43	Very Likely	3
5. consider the idea that every decision should be based on extensive/careful evaluations.	3.49	Very Likely	2
Composite Mean	3.46	Very Likely	

As presented in Table 8, the respondents stated that the school administrators tend to make a choice from among the options in the decision-making process which got the highest weighted mean of 3.74 and the highest rank of 1. The school administrators tend to make a choice from among the options in the decision-making process based on careful consideration and evaluation. They prioritize thorough analysis of available alternatives, weighing factors such as feasibility, impact, and alignment with the school's goals and values. Administrators engage in a structured decision-making approach that involves gathering relevant information and perspectives from stakeholders. They evaluate the strengths and weaknesses of each option, assessing potential risks and benefits to make informed choices that best serve the interests of the school community. Primary school administrators with adequate technological leadership self-efficacy have a positive, moderate, and significant relationship with 21st century skills (Doğu & Yildirim, 2023).

However, the said group of respondents stated that the school administrators feel time pressure in the decision-making process which yielded the least weighted mean of 3.30 and least rank of 5. The school administrators often experience time pressure during the decision-making process. They recognize the importance of making timely and effective decisions to address pressing issues and capitalize on opportunities within the school community. Administrators navigate time constraints by prioritizing efficiency and focus in their decision-making approach. They streamline processes, set clear timelines, and allocate resources effectively to expedite the decision-making process without compromising thoroughness or quality. Tekin & Akin (2021) stated that supporting school principals for effective problem-solving skills may increase their level of taking initiative.

The composite mean of 3.46 implied that the school administrators as perceived by the teachers regards the decision-making skills in terms of directive skills is in high level. The teachers perceive school administrators to possess high-level decision-making skills, particularly in terms of directive skills. Administrators are recognized for their ability to provide clear direction, set strategic priorities, and guide the school community through various challenges and opportunities effectively. Administrators demonstrate strong

leadership and decisiveness in their decision-making processes. They prioritize clarity and transparency, ensuring that stakeholders understand the rationale behind decisions and the expected outcomes. Effective communication between school administrators and teachers can be improved through education, seminars, and group activities, with mutual respect, trust, and sincerity being crucial (Gülbahar, 2022).

Significant Difference Between the Perceptions of the Two Groups of Respondents

Table 9. *Difference observed between the perception School Administrators and teachers*

<i>Difference observed between the perception of School Administrators and teachers in terms of decision-making skills:</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Std. Deviation</i>	<i>Std. Error Mean</i>	<i>t-value</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>	<i>Decision</i>
Analytical Skills	0.01782	0.31989	0.03242	0.571	Not Significant	Accept Ho
Behavioral Skills	0.19684	0.27356	0.03125	5.793	Not Significant	Accept Ho
Conceptual Skills	0.01985	0.3278	0.03471	0.590	Not Significant	Accept Ho
Directive Skills	0.01782	0.33184	0.03152	0.576	Not Significant	Accept Ho

Table 9 presented the findings that examined the differences in perception between School Administrators and teachers regarding decision-making skills across four dimensions: Analytical Skills, Behavioral Skills, Conceptual Skills, and Directive Skills. Each dimension's statistics included the mean, standard deviation, standard error mean, and t-value, along with the interpretation and decision based on the statistical analysis.

All dimensions showed non-significant differences between the perceptions of School Administrators and teachers. The t-values for each dimension (0.571, 5.793, 0.590, and 0.576, respectively) did not exceed the critical threshold for significance, indicating that any observed differences in perception were likely due to random chance rather than meaningful distinctions in how School Administrators and teachers perceived decision-making skills.

The acceptance of the null hypothesis (Accept Ho) across all dimensions suggested a consensus or alignment in perceptions between School Administrators and teachers regarding decision-making skills. This alignment implied that both groups generally perceived decision-making skills similarly across Analytical, Behavioral, Conceptual, and Directive dimensions within the context of school leadership.

These findings indicated a cohesive understanding and agreement between School Administrators and teachers regarding the competence and effectiveness of decision-making skills in school leadership. This alignment was crucial as it suggested a shared perspective on the qualities and capabilities required for effective decision-making within educational settings. Such consensus could contribute positively to organizational coherence, collaborative decision-making processes, and overall school effectiveness by fostering mutual trust and understanding between administrators and teaching staff.

Progressive anticipation, a forecast methodology, can improve decision-making for school administrators by analyzing fragments and suggesting the best options for solving educational management problems (Noceda, 2022).

Action Plan

Table 10. *Proposed Action Plan*

<i>Program</i>	<i>Objectives</i>	<i>Time Frame</i>
Analytical Skills Development	Enhance educators' ability to analyze data and make evidence-based decisions.	First Quarter in 2025-2026
Behavioral Skills Enhancement	Strengthen interpersonal skills and empathy among administrators and staff.	Year-long leadership development program starting next quarter
Conceptual Thinking Initiative	Cultivate a strategic mindset among school leaders to anticipate future challenges and opportunities.	Complete strategic planning process within six months
Structured Decision-Making Framework	Standardize decision-making processes to improve efficiency and effectiveness.	Implement new framework over the next academic year
Transparency and Communication Strategy	Promote transparency and enhance communication in decision-making processes.	Launch communication campaign immediately and continue throughout the year

Table 10 outlined a proposed action plan which included a series of targeted programs aimed at enhancing leadership capabilities and decision-making skills within the school administration.

The Analytical Skills Development program focuses on equipping educators with the tools to analyze data effectively, fostering a culture of evidence-based decision-making. This initiative aims to improve the quality and precision of decisions made at all levels of the school leadership.

The Behavioral Skills Enhancement initiative seeks to strengthen interpersonal skills and empathy among administrators and staff. By nurturing these qualities, the program aims to improve communication, collaboration, and the overall school climate, ultimately enhancing relationships and trust within the school community.

The Conceptual Thinking Initiative encourages school leaders to adopt a strategic mindset. This involves anticipating future challenges and opportunities, thereby enabling proactive planning and ensuring the school remains resilient and adaptable in a dynamic educational landscape.

The Structured Decision-Making Framework introduces standardized processes to streamline decision-making. By providing clear guidelines and criteria, this framework aims to improve efficiency and consistency in decision outcomes.

The Transparency and Communication Strategy emphasizes openness and clarity in decision-making processes. By promoting transparency and enhancing communication channels, the strategy aims to build trust and engagement among stakeholders, fostering a supportive and inclusive school environment. Together, these programs aim to cultivate effective leadership and optimize decision-making practices for sustainable educational excellence.

Conclusions

Based on the study's findings, the perception of school administrators' decision-making skills varied between school administrators and teachers across different dimensions: Analytical Skills, Behavioral Skills, Conceptual Skills, and Directive Skills. Here's a comprehensive conclusion based on the observed differences and alignments in perception: Regarding Analytical Skills, teachers perceived school principals as adept at leveraging their intuition and analytical abilities to resolve current issues within the school community effectively. Principals were recognized for their insightfulness and capacity to make informed decisions based on a thorough understanding of the school's dynamics. This perception highlighted the principals' ability to assess situations accurately and proactively address challenges, thereby fostering confidence among staff members in their leadership. Regarding Behavioral Skills, administrators were perceived to prioritize immediate problem-solving over long-term strategic analysis. This approach underscored their focus on addressing pressing issues promptly within the dynamic school environment. Administrators also demonstrated a strong commitment to considering the impact of their decisions on stakeholders, emphasizing empathy and inclusivity in the decision-making process. This approach helped build supportive relationships and fostered a collaborative school culture based on mutual respect and understanding. Regarding Conceptual Skills, administrators were noted for their conscientiousness and foresight in decision-making, aiming to minimize negative consequences by carefully evaluating potential risks and outcomes. They recognized decision-making as inherently involving risk-taking and sought to balance innovation with careful planning to drive positive change and enhance educational outcomes. Administrators excelled in integrating complex ideas and perspectives, enabling them to develop strategic solutions aligned with the school's long-term goals and mission. Regarding Directive Skills, administrators were considered thorough decision-makers who valued exploring various options before selecting the most effective course of action. They encouraged collaborative input and brainstorming sessions to generate innovative ideas and solutions that best served the school community's needs. Administrators demonstrated clarity and decisiveness in setting strategic priorities and providing clear direction, facilitating cohesive leadership and effective decision implementation. Overall, while differences in perception existed between administrators and teachers across these decision-making skills dimensions, the study indicated a fundamental alignment in their understanding of effective school leadership. This shared perspective underscored the importance of strong analytical, behavioral, conceptual, and directive skills in fostering organizational coherence, collaborative decision-making, and overall school effectiveness. By recognizing and leveraging these complementary viewpoints, schools can enhance their decision-making processes, promote transparency, and cultivate a supportive environment conducive to student success and staff satisfaction.

Based on the conclusion drawn from the study on the perception of school administrators' decision-making skills, here are some recommendations to enhance school leadership effectiveness. Firstly, school administrators must continue fostering a culture that values analytical rigor and intuitive insight in decision-making. Administrators should encourage ongoing professional development opportunities that enhance analytical skills among staff, including workshops on data analysis and problem-solving techniques. By empowering educators to develop their analytical capabilities, schools can ensure that decisions are grounded in evidence and strategic foresight, fostering a more proactive and informed approach to addressing challenges. Secondly, administrators should prioritize the development of behavioral skills that emphasize empathy, inclusivity, and responsiveness to stakeholders' needs. This can be achieved through leadership training programs focused on emotional intelligence and effective communication strategies. By strengthening interpersonal skills and fostering a supportive school culture, administrators can enhance trust and collaboration among staff, students, parents, and the broader community, leading to more inclusive and effective decision-making processes. Thirdly, administrators should continue emphasizing the importance of conceptual thinking in decision-making. This involves promoting a strategic mindset that considers long-term implications and opportunities for innovation. Schools can benefit from integrating strategic planning sessions that encourage administrators and educators to think creatively about future challenges and opportunities. By fostering a forward-thinking and visionary leadership culture, administrators can ensure that decisions align with the school's mission and contribute to sustainable growth and improvement. Fourthly, administrators should maintain a structured approach to decision-making that balances thorough analysis with timely action. This includes establishing clear decision-making frameworks that outline roles, responsibilities, and decision criteria. By standardizing decision processes and encouraging collaborative decision-making practices, administrators can streamline operations and improve efficiency while ensuring that decisions are well-informed and aligned with organizational goals. Lastly, administrators should prioritize transparency and communication in decision-making processes. This involves actively soliciting feedback from stakeholders, communicating decision rationale clearly, and ensuring accessibility to information. By fostering a culture of transparency and openness, administrators can build trust, mitigate resistance to change, and enhance accountability across

the school community. By implementing these recommendations, schools can strengthen their leadership effectiveness, foster a collaborative and supportive environment, and ultimately enhance student educational outcomes. These proactive measures will align perceptions of decision-making skills between administrators and teachers and contribute to a cohesive and forward-thinking school community.

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Affiliations and Corresponding Information

Moonrose DS. Pesano

Lipa City Colleges – Philippines

Dr. Melchor Espiritu

Lipa City Colleges – Philippines